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**First record of *Syneches muscarius*
(Fabricius, 1794) (Diptera: Empididae:
Hybotinae) from Ukraine**

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The dancing flies of genus *Syneches* (Empididae: Hybotinae: Hybotini, sometimes as Hybotidae: Hybotinae) are represented by more than 150 species worldwide (Pape & Thompson, 2020), and a dozen of palaeartic species occurring predominantly in Far East of Asia; the single species species occur (Chvála & Kovalev, 1989; Chvála, 2013).

A single specimen of an unidentified fly species was collected by the first author; its photos were published (Mishustin, 2020) and included with coordinates on the UkrBIN site (UkrBIN, 2020). Later, it was identified as *Syneches muscarius* (Fabricius, 1794), a species previously unrecorded from Ukraine.

***Syneches muscarius* (Fabricius, 1794) (Figs 1–2)**

Material. Ukraine: Kherson, 46.641742°N, 32.619185°E, 03.10.2020, 1 ♀ (Mishustin) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe, from Great Britain and Spain to European Territory of Russia (Chvála & Kovalev, 1989; Chvála, 2013); Ukraine (**first record** of genus and species).

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Figs 1–2. *Syneches muscarius*, female habitus: 1 — laterally, 2 — dorsally.

References

- Chvála, M. 2013. Hybotidae. In: *Fauna Europaea: Diptera. Fauna Europaea version 2017.06*, <https://fauna-eu.org>.
- Chvála, M. & Kovalev, V.G. 1989. Hybotidae. In: *Soós A. & Papp L. (eds.) Catalogue of Palaearctic Diptera. Volume 6. Therevidae — Empididae*. Akadémiai Kiadó & Elsevier, Budapest & Amsterdam: 174–227.
- Mishustin, R. I. 2020. *Syneches muscarius*. Image ID #181914–181917. In: UkrBIN: Ukrainian Biodiversity Information Network [public project & web application]. UkrBIN, Database on Biodiversity Information. Available from: <http://ukrbn.com/index.php?id=371150> (Accessed: 21.11.2020).
- Pape, T. & Thompson, F.C. (eds) 2020. *Syneches*. In: Roskov Y.; Ower G.; Orrell T.; Nicolson D.; Bailly N.; Kirk P.M.; Bourgoin T.; DeWalt R.E.; Decock W.; Nieukerken E. van; Penev L.; eds. *Species 2000 & ITIS Catalogue of Life, 2020-09-01 Beta*. Digital resource at www.catalogueoflife.org/col. Species 2000: Naturalis, Leiden, the Netherlands. Available from: <http://www.catalogueoflife.org/col/browse/tree/id/85463c9bc58cc1279249989376479fd7> (Accessed: November 21, 2020).
- UkrBIN. 2020. *UkrBIN: Ukrainian Biodiversity Information Network [public project & web application]*. UkrBIN, Database on Biodiversity Information. Available from: <http://www.ukrbn.com> (Accessed: 09.10.2020).